

Action Plan

Cooperation and clustering transformative change projects and initiatives

31 August 2023

Jeanne Nel, Rosalie van Dam, Roel During, Zoe van Eldik, Judith Westerink, Amy Wortel

Technical References

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1 PU = Public
 PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
 RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	Date	Author
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Annex V0.2	1 August 2023	Sebastien Kaye, Agnes Zolyomi, Jeanne Nel, Rosalie Van Dam, Thirze Hermans, Verina Ingram, Robin Dianoux
Annex V0.1	23 March 2023	Jeanne Nel,

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31 August 2023

1 Introduction

There is growing agreement on the need for transformative change to address global challenges, such as biodiversity loss. However, there is less agreement about *what* transformative change entails and *how* it can be achieved. To address these knowledge gaps, the Horizon Europe Work Programme funded 11 Horizon Europe-funded projects with a core focus on enabling transformative change for biodiversity (Figure 1).

The European Research Executive Agency (REA) has requested that these so-called 'sister projects' include collaborative activities in their workplan to better harness the synergies and common areas of work in the contexts of transformative change for biodiversity, to maximize the impact and exploitation of results of the projects and facilitate feedback to policy. Moreover there is cooperation with other relevant EU initiatives, such as BioAgora which is setting up the Science Service for biodiversity.

BIOTraCes' partners are part of other transformative change and biodiversity conservation national and international projects and networks, as for example IPBES, IPCC, Altnet, CBD. Exchange of (new) knowledge is also taking place between these initiatives.

This report summarizes work already done and forthcoming plans by BIOTraCes on fostering collaboration and creation of synergies and cooperation with sister projects and initiatives of interest, including Horizon Europe activities such as the European Partnerships and Missions.

Figure 1: Sister projects as listed on BIOTraCes <https://www.biotraces.eu/project/#sister>

Deliverable 5.8: Action Plan for Clustering Activities

31 August 2023

Table 1 List of sister projects, hyperlinked to their websites, and showing the coordinator and communicator contacts

Project	Coordination	Coordination contact	Communication	Communication contact
BAMBOO	Francesca Verones	Francesca.verones@ntnu.no	Sedona Anderson	sedona.anderson@ntnu.no
BIONEXT	Anna-Stiina – Heiskanen Soile Oinonen Jari Koskiaho	anna-stiina.heiskanen@syke.fi Soile.Oinonen@syke.fi Jari.Koskiaho@syke.fi	Maija Airos	maija.airos@syke.fi
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BIOTRAILS	Raffaele Giordano	raffaele.giordano@cnr.it	Frini Lazaraou Maren Tornow Evangelina Drakou Marit Langheim	frinil@ebos.com.cy tornow@adelphi.de e.drakou@hua.gr langheim@adelphi.de
BioValue	Maria Partário Rute Martins	mariapartidario@tecnico.ulisboa.pt rutemartins@tecnico.ulisboa.pt	Chiara Bartolacci Mattia Benedetti	chiara.bartolacci@icons.it mattia.benedetti@icons.it
CLEVER	Jan Börner Yaghoob Jafari Fernanda Martinelli	jborner@uni-bonn.de yaghoob.jafari@ilr.uni-bonn.de fernanda.martinelli@uni-bonn.de	Rosa Castañeda - -	rosa.castaneda@efi.int - -
PLANET4B	Ilkhom Soliev Alex Franklin Agnes Zolyomi Torsten Waehler	ilkhom.soliev@zirs.uni-halle.de ac0569@coventry.ac.uk agnes.zolyomi@unep-wcmc.org torsten.waehler@zirs.uni-halle.de	Zsuzsanna Kiraly	kiraly@jougykft.hu
RAINFOREST SUSTAIN	Francesca Verones Martin Lok Fae Rinaldo	Francesca.verones@ntnu.no Martin.lok@capitalscoalition.org fae.rinaldo@capitalscoalition.org	Francesca Verones David Thomas	francesca.verones@ntnu.no david.thomas@capitalscoalition.org
TC4BE	Thirze Hermans Verina Ingram Valerie Nelson	Thirze.hermans@wur.nl Verina.Ingram@wur.nl V.J.Nelson@gre.ac.uk	Josh Muhumuza Adrienne Martin	J.R.Muhumuza@greenwich.ac.uk A.M.Martin@greenwich.ac.uk
TRANSPATH	Francisco Alpizar Jeanne Nel	francisco.alpizar@wur.nl jeanne.nel@wur.nl	Teodor Metodiev Carla Stoyanova	t.metodiev@pensoft.net c.stoyanova@pensoft.net

2 Action Plan for Clustering Activities

The collaborative activities with the sister projects will evolve as findings mature, and the specific engagement needs emerge. Some projects last only three years, BIOTraCes lasts four years. We will investigate how we can align timelines to maintain momentum. In addition to collaborating with the sister projects, we are in close collaboration with BioAgora, which is a flagship Horizon Europe project currently setting up the Science Service for biodiversity. Members of BIOTraCes are specifically involved in setting up a framework to examine the transformative potential of science-policy interfaces. The work in BIOTraCes provides valuable insights.

To synergise our work and maximise inter-project impact and exploitation of results, BIOTraCes commits to three planned activities with relevant sister project(s) (Figure 2). A further activity of *ad hoc* online meetings between BIOTraCes and other sister projects to signify our commitment to collaborating with sister projects where we identify an opportunities or needs. For example, in a case study or conference or policy event where collaboration can mutually enhance advancing knowledge or implementation.

Each of these activities is explained in further detail below.

QUARTER	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3				YEAR 4			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Maintain Working Group on "Values, Norms and Justice"	x		x		x		x		x		x		x		x	
Annual events with sister project(s)			x					x				x				x
Case Study Reflections across sister project(s)								x							x	
Online ad hoc meetings with sister project(s)	when needed															

Figure 2: Timeline of collaborative activities with sister projects

2.1 Maintain Working Group 3 on 'Values, Norms and Justice'

Collaboration across the sister projects is encouraged through the establishment of three working groups:

Working group 1. Biodiversity Nexus, towards a nature positive society

Working Group 2. Production, consumption and global trade, including Business and Financing

Working Group 3: Values, norms, justice and societal agency to accelerate transformations for biodiversity

BIOTraCes and PLANET4B currently co-lead the Working Group 3 on Values, Norms and Justice. A living 'Action Plan' document is co-created with partner input from projects within WG3 (Annex 1). This document sets out an initial 6 month plan. Currently, there are 4 general activities, which will be updated upon a meeting of BIOTraCes, PLANET4B, TC4BE, TRANSPATH at the first annual event, planned 24-27 October 2023:

- Mapping project synergies in a shared document
- Meetings to coordinate activities (online and in person)
- Learning and knowledge exchange that deep-dive into particular topics
- Evolving perspectives on the social justice components of our sister projects

2.2 Annual events with sister projects

During the first cluster meeting in Brussels, it became clear that several of the WG3 members were going to be represented at the 2023 Earth Systems Governance conference, October 2023, including members from BIOTraCes, PLANET4B, TC4BE and TRANSPATH.

We have agreed to support and contribute to each other's approved sessions, for example by being a discussant in a panel. In particular, there is one interactive session, which we will try to design around, eliciting reflections from participating sister projects on "Value-oriented transformative governance for biodiversity".

And we will arrange a side HYBRID meeting during the conference to discuss:

- Identifying a potential joint session at a 2024 conference
- Identifying a topic for an online learning event between the sister projects
- Discussing what format the case study reflections session could take
- Consideration of a joint PhD webinar

2.3 Case study reflections across sister 'projects' 2024/ 2025

This is a potential joint activity that BIOTraCes, TC4BE and PLANET4B have identified for some time towards the second half of 2024 or early 2025. We would map the joint spread of case studies in the sister projects and hear about them from each other. We are likely to focus on one or both of the following issues: setting up case studies for transformative research; mapping promising leverage points and levers across case studies (similarities and differences). This will be further discussed at the 2023 Earth Systems Governance conference.

3 Joint activities completed

3.1 Working Group 3 on "Values, Norms and Justice"

During the first six months, BIOTraCes worked with PLANET4B to co-develop a first draft of the Working Group 3 Action Plan. The continuation and co-leadership will be discussed at the 2023 Earth Systems Governance conference. BIOTraCes are happy to continue to play a strong role in ensuring its continuity, and have been involved in several coordination meetings as described in section 3.2.

3.2 Online meetings with sister project(s) and other initiatives

A joint workshop was organised on the 29th of June between project representatives of BIOTraCes, BIOTRAILS, BioAgora, TRANSPATH and PLANET4B to discuss potential joint actions. The activities laid out in Working Group 3 Annex 1 capture and build on what was agreed at this workshop.

3.3 Participation in umbrella website for communication

BIOTraCes is participating with BioValue, TRANSPATH and other projects to form umbrella websites of communicators lists and stakeholder lists, and repost each other's social media posts.

Annex 1: Action plan for Working Group 3 on values, norms and justice, submitted by co-lead PLANET4B

Action Plan of Transformative Change Clustering

Deliverable number: D5.11

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PLANET4B

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

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PLANET4B

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

Key deliverable information

Project acronym **PLANET4B**

Project title	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
Starting date	01 st November 2022
Duration	36 months
Website	https://planet4b.eu/
Project coordination and scientific lead team	Ilkhom Soliev; Alex Franklin; Agnes Zolyomi; Torsten Wähler

Deliverable number **D5.11**

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Task leader	UNEP-WCMC
Dissemination level	Public
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Deliverable description

The action plan includes mapped synergies and relevant actions with the Horizon Europe transformative change cluster projects.

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0.3	Draft	18/07/2023	Authors: Sebastien Kaye (UNEP-WCMC), Agnes Zolyomi (UNEP-WCMC)
1.0	Final	28/07/2023	Reviewer: Ilkhom Soliev (MLU)

Contributors to action/intervention directly leading to this deliverable

Claire Brown (UNEP-WCMC), Ilkhom Soliev (MLU), Torsten Wähler (MLU)

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Definition
BAMBOO	Biodiversity and trade: mitigating the impacts of non-food biomass and global supply chains
BIOAGORA	Connecting biodiversity knowledge and decision making
BIONEXT	The Biodiversity Nexus – Triggering Transformative Change for Sustainability
BIOTraCes	Biodiversity and transformative change for plural and nature-positive societies
BIOTRAILS	Nexus framework for biodiversity-relevant transformative change
BIOVALUE	Biodiversity value in spatial policy and planning leveraging multi-level and transformative change
CLEVER	Creating Leverage to enhance biodiversity outcomes of global biomass trade
EU B&B Platform	European Business and Biodiversity Platform
INRAE	L'Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement
MLU	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg
PLANET4B	Understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
RAINFOREST	Co-produced transformative knowledge to accelerate change for biodiversity
SUSTAIN	Strengthening Understanding and Strategies of business to Assess and Integrate Nature
TC4BE	Transformative Change in Telecoupled Agrofood Systems for Biodiversity and Equity
TCC	Transformative Change Cluster
TRANSPATH	Transformative pathways for synergising just biodiversity and climate actions
UNEP-WCMC	United Nations Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre
WG3	Working Group 3
WUR	Wageningen University & Research

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1 Introduction

To increase cooperation among the Transformative Change Cluster (TCC) Horizon Europe projects¹, three working groups were created involving relevant TCC projects. The creation of working groups and the selection of their topics were initiated by the European Commission. The names of the TCC working groups are as follows:

- Towards a nature positive society: the Biodiversity Nexus. Strengthening links between biodiversity, water, food, energy, transport, climate, and health [Working Group 1]
- Production, consumption and global trade, including Business and Financing. How can the private sector contribute to Transformative Change? [Working Group 2]
- Values, norms, justice and societal agency to accelerate transformations for biodiversity. Democratic decision-making, Intersectionality, Behaviours, Gender, Beliefs and Community knowledge for biodiversity [Working Group 3]

The aim of fostering collaboration with other projects² within Working Group 3 (WG3), titled 'Values, norms, justice and societal agency to accelerate transformations for biodiversity' based on shared synergies, is to increase reach and uptake of project activities and outcomes to boost joint impact. This document lays out a joint action plan based on synergistic areas of work within Horizon Europe TCC projects' WG3. The joint action plan outlines different types of collaboration, provides objectives, outputs and a timeline for coordinating joint work and details steps to follow for further identifying shared synergies.

This joint deliverable co-produced and submitted by all WG3 projects has been co-created with partner input from projects³ within WG3. The action plan will be built upon and expanded throughout the lifecycle of the TCC projects that make up WG3 through regular collaborative partner input and feedback from members of the working group as well as across the two other TCC working groups. This joint action plan works as both an internal reference for members of WG3 project consortiums as well as guidance for members of other TCC projects on our intention to establish collaborative activities.

1.1 Background

This deliverable seeks to develop a joint action plan of activities including mapping synergies and relevant action within the context of WG3, which was initially formed at the 1st Cluster Event for TCC projects in Brussels. On 17th March 2023, representatives of all TCC Horizon Europe projects and representatives of additional relevant EU funded projects⁴ met in Brussels for the 1st Cluster Event for the TCC projects, led by the European Research Executive Agency. This meeting was initiated by the European Commission and had as one of its purposes the initiation of the three

¹ The 11 Horizon Europe Projects on Transformative Change for Biodiversity are as follows: BAMBOO, BIONEXT, BIOTraCes, BIOTRAILS, BIOVALUE, CLEVER, PLANET4B, RAINFOREST, SUSTAIN, TC4BE, TRANSPATH

² The projects that make up WG3 are: BIOTraCes, BIOTRAILS, BIOVALUE, BioAgora

³ These projects are: BIOTraCes, BIOTRAILS, BioAgora and PLANET4B

⁴ These additional EU funded initiatives present are: BioAgora, CircHive, SELINA, NetworkNature, EU B&B Platform, Biodiversa+

Working Groups within the TCC. The meeting was organised by Unit B.3 “Biodiversity, Circular Economy and Environment” and brought together the selected 11 Horizon Europe projects on transformative change for biodiversity to identify synergies and common areas of work. At the in-person meeting, project representatives presented their projects, shared ideas and were encouraged to join three different working groups that were established with the aim of maximising synergies and joint work to increase impact in certain key thematic areas present across the TCC projects.

Sebastien Kaye (PLANET4B) and Jeanne Nel (BIOTRACES/TRANSPATH) volunteered to coordinate the ‘Values, norms, justice and societal agency to accelerate transformations for biodiversity’ Working Group (WG3). As such, WG3 is the working group that this joint action plan focusses on. A joint workshop was organised on the 29th of June between project representatives of BIOTraCes, BIOTRAILS, BioAgora, TRANSPATH and PLANET4B to discuss potential joint actions. The activities laid out in part 2 below seek to capture and build on what was agreed at this workshop.

1.2 Objectives

The joint action plan has a twofold objective. **The first objective** is to foster collaboration between TCC projects based on shared synergies to increase the reach, impact and uptake of the outputs of the Horizon Europe projects. This will be done from the basis that the cross-fertilization of ideas, collaborative work and joint coordination of synergistic activities and joint outputs can lead to producing results that are greater than the sum of their parts. **The second objective** is to establish an agreed timeline and process to guide how collaboration on joint activities will take place.

2 Activities and determining joint actions

The below joint activities will be conducted iteratively by members of WG3 and have deliberately been designed to generate joint actions which have yet to be further specified at the time of writing this deliverable. As such, the activities are adaptable and seek to feed into a joint programme of shared work which will evolve and be further determined throughout the lifecycle of the projects that make up WG3 based on the resources available.

Activity 1: Mapping synergies

The objective of this activity is to identify shared synergies between WG3 projects around which joint actions can take place. To map relevant synergies and determine joint actions, a shared document outlining all working group project deliverables and their deadlines will be created. This will act as a reference point for mapping synergies and determining joint actions across projects within the working group. As such, different types of collaboration such as knowledge sharing or knowledge co-production can be undertaken between projects within WG3 and organised through WG3 meetings or bilateral meetings between specific WG3 projects. A foreseeable output for this activity is the creation of a shared document outlining WG3 project deliverables and deadlines which will act as a point of reference for determining joint actions.

Timeline for activity 1

The shared document outlining WG3 deliverables will be created by the end of September 2023 to act as a point of reference during future WG3 meetings. Mapping

synergies will be a continuous process that is incorporated into the topics of discussion of WG3 meetings.

Activity 2: Meetings to coordinate working group activities

The objective of this activity is to create time to coordinate joint actions based on identified synergies that fit within the remit of the themes within WG3. This activity will involve project coordinators, specific project representatives or work package leads within projects that make up WG3 and would seek to plan our collective learning and the preparation of joint activities as a working group. The online meetings would aim to reach a level of shared understanding to conduct transformative research across disciplines and work towards establishing joint activities between projects. As well as acting as a space to plan and coordinate joint activities, each coordination meeting will seek to address a particular topic relevant to the themes of the working group. The initial meeting will relate to the challenges of setting up a transformative change project. The topic of each future meeting will be determined by a vote of different suggested meeting topics, at the end of each preceding meeting. The output of these meetings will seek to establish further joint actions and coordination of collaborative activities.

Timeline for activity 2

Coordination meetings will occur three times a year with the next coordination meeting due to take place at the planned Earth Systems Governance Conference (24 – 27 October 2023). The specific date and times of each further meeting will be determined through consultation with project coordinators or representatives of WG3 in order to ensure as many people as possible will be able to attend.

Activity 3: Learning and knowledge exchange meetings

The objective of this activity will be to create in depth explorations of topics relating to WG3 through harnessing forums at scientific conferences or other events. This activity will consist of in-person or hybrid meetings at specified events such as conferences or knowledge exchange workshops and will be open to the wider TCC projects' consortiums to join. WG3 partners and their broader consortiums will have a chance to attend (in-person or online), participate in or present a deep-dive into particular topics relevant to WG3. As such, this activity will be open to all members of WG3 as well as other members of the TCC including PhD students to attend in-person or online, should the meetings take a hybrid format.

Timeline for activity 3

The initial learning exchange meeting will take place within the context of the Earth Systems Governance Conference where at least three sessions will be led by TC4BE, BIOTraCeS, TRANSPATH and PLANET4B leading and participating in a panel discussions. An open invitation to all other Horizon Europe TCC projects will be extended. Beyond this first session, learning and knowledge exchange meetings will occur once a year at a minimum with the timing and details of the event each year to be determined by members of WG3.

Activity 4: Evolving perspectives on social justice in relation to transformative change for biodiversity

The objective of this activity is to create space for joint reflection and action based on considerations for the social justice component to our projects. A template (Annex I) has been developed by Robin Dianoux from BioAgora to help project partners reflect

on how to incorporate social justice dimensions into their projects. Building from this perspective routed in fostering a dialogue on the relationship between social justice and transformative change, a dialogue workshop within WG3 will be organised to discuss the social justice component to our projects. More specifically this workshop will seek to develop a dialogue between project partners on social justice, why it matters in transformative change research and how it can be incorporated into research, policy and practice. The outcome of this initial workshop will collectively inform a decision taken by those present regarding whether future workshops that address the topic of social justice as it relates to the various topics of our WG3, would be welcome. More broadly, the topic of social justice will seek to be addressed within our coordination meetings.

Timeline for activity 4

The timeline and frequency of meetings for activity 4 will be determined at the first meeting for the activity, taking place in Q4 2023. After the first meeting and shared reflection on using and thinking through the template that was prepared relating to social justice considerations, WG3 members will be invited to determine whether further meetings should take place to discuss and collectively work on social justice issues within our projects.

3 Management of activities

Further joint activities will begin from the latter half of 2023 and will continue until the end of the project cycles involved (2025-2026). The organisation of meetings for the above activities will be facilitated by WG3's coordinators (Jeanne Nel and Sebastien Kaye) with the consultation of WG3 participants to determine meeting times and meeting topics. The chairing order of meetings will be distributed amongst WG3's participants and an agenda will be circulated beforehand providing WG3 participants the opportunity to comment on or add items to the agenda. Project partners will also be encouraged to self-organise joint activities based on identified synergies and opportunities for collaboration that arise. Updates relating to ongoing joint activities will be provided during WG3 coordination meetings. Reporting on joint events will be made in a specific template and saved on a shared WG3 sharepoint folder held by UNEP-WCMC (with access provided to all WG3 projects) in order to keep a record of meetings and joint work.

4 Conclusions and next steps

Increasing cooperation and work to address joint activities will be an iterative process which will require the participation and active engagement of members of WG3. Through this engagement, members of WG3 will together explore the working groups' themes in order to generate shared collaboration with an aim to deepen and maximise the reach and uptake of the WG3's projects. This action plan has been designed for it to be flexible and adaptable to changes as well as incorporating future joint activities which have yet to be identified and planned. The initial dates for the first meetings for activities 1 and 4 will be determined by polling the members of WG3 for their availability in Q4 of 2023. The first coordination meeting (activity 2) will seek to build consensus and participatory agreement on the details and meeting topics of the action plan.

Statement on ethics

The content described in this joint deliverable was produced together with the contribution of projects BIOTraCes, BIOTRAILS, BIOVALUE, BioAgora and PLANET4B through several workshops, and constitutes as a joint product of these projects.

Annex I – Template for addressing social justice considerations within projects

Values, norms, justice and societal agency to accelerate transformations for biodiversity Working Group of the “Transformative Change for Biodiversity” Cluster of Horizon Europe-funded projects

This short introductory reminder is based on the recent article from Martin et al. (2020) which offers a succinct summary of the environmental justice stakes in attempts to generate transformative changes.

Changes in the name of “ecology” and “environmental protection” can go in many directions and take numerous shapes, many of which potentially leading to reinforcing social inequalities in the name of environmental protection. Indeed, transformations can lead to redistributions which “cannot be assumed to have homogeneous effects across diverse groups of people” and, taking into account the context of unequal power, there is a risk that the resulting impacts may affect disproportionately already marginalised people. Thus, any attempt of changing or transforming a situation should be done with a great care toward the consequences of direct and indirect changes towards vulnerable population and with regard to power relations.

As the transformations are designed with an attention on environmental justice, one should be attentive to the impact of the transformation on the three dimensions that are commonly put forward, and which relates to issues of distribution, procedure and recognition: “Distributive justice refers to the allocation of environmental costs and benefits. Procedural justice refers to the decision-making process — in particular, who gets to participate. Justice as recognition refers to the political and cultural status afforded to identity groups defined by social characteristics such as gender, ethnicity, or worldview, intersecting with spatial and historical contexts. These concerns are typically linked.”

As they also point the importance “to emphasize the challenge of addressing not only the unequal outcomes of environmental change, but also the underlying distributions of power that produce these inequalities”, this implies that ‘just’ transformative environmental change needs to be premised on redistribution of power (or at least a consideration of the existing distribution of power structuring the observed phenomena).

A few guidance notes for filling the template:

Importance to not just focus on expected consequences of the work that your project is undertaking but on the actual practical methods used to address, include and assess these issues within the course of your research and transformative activities.

While a person from each project could potentially quickly answers the following questions (check!), the idea behind our group and behind this small task is above all to generate ongoing questioning, reflexivity and discussions of those themes both between projects as well as within each project, so feel free to discuss it collectively before actually filling the template!

Besides, this exercise is equally about what our projects already do and the support we can provide to others as it is about how we can improve and the type of help and tools that could help us acknowledge more these themes.

Finally, we could hope that bringing these questions in our projects can help keeping alive an attention to the relations and possible interdependences between the environmental issues at hand and other societal issues.

Reference: Adrian Martin, M. Teresa Armijos, Brendan Coolsaet, Neil Dawson, Gareth A. S. Edwards, Roger Few, Nicole Gross-Camp, Iokiñe Rodríguez, Heike Schroeder, Mark G. L. Tebboth & Carole S. White (2020) Environmental Justice and Transformations to Sustainability, *Environment: Science and Policy for Sustainable Development*, 62:6, 19-30, DOI: [10.1080/00139157.2020.1820294](https://doi.org/10.1080/00139157.2020.1820294)

Template for assessing how projects deal with social and environmental justice

Name of the project:

Is a concept of justice used in your project? Y/N

if so which one and why it is relevant for your project?

In which aspects of the issue you're focusing on it is addressed?

Where does your project may potentially overlook issues of justice and could better integrate them?

How do you assess in practice (through which methods) existing justice issues and the potential impacts of the transformative changes your project aims to generate on those issues?

In particular, are you addressing the following issues or use the following justice lenses?

- Issues of distribution? Y/N If so, where:
- Issues of procedure? Y/N If so, where:
- Issues of recognition? Y/N If so, where:

If not, could you consider addressing them or include an assessment of the impact of the transformations your project aims to generate on those issues? If so, in which particular aspect of your project?

Finally, do you feel that you have sufficient capacity (specialists, resources, methods) to address these questions or that you may need to investigate it further and/or have some support? If so, of which kind?

For those wanting to go deeper, you can address the themes in this way:

Justice as distribution:

- Does your project evaluate how environmental costs and benefits appear to be distributed in the issues your project focuses on and wants to 'transform'?
 - If so, how it is done and how it could be improved?
 - If not, in which parts/tasks/focuses of your project could this be addressed and how?

- Does your project plan on evaluating how this current distribution may be modified by your project?
 - If so, how it is done and how it could be improved?
 - If not, in which parts/tasks/focuses of your project could this be addressed and how?

Justice as procedure:

- Does your project evaluate who gets to participate in the decisions currently affecting the situation your project focuses on and wants to 'transform'?
 - If so, how it is done and how it could be improved?
 - If not, in which parts/tasks/focuses of your project could this be addressed and how?

- Does your project plan on evaluating how this current participation may be modified by your project?
 - If so, how it is done and how it could be improved?
 - If not, in which parts/tasks/focuses of your project could this be addressed and how?

Justice as recognition (intersectionality analysis):

- Does your project evaluate whether inequalities and discriminations based on class, race, species, gender and generation (as well as their intersection) potentially impact the issues your project focuses on and wants to 'transform'?
 - If so, how it is done and how it could be improved?
 - If not, in which parts/tasks/focuses of your project could this be addressed and how?

- Does your project plan on evaluating how the inequalities and discriminations based on class, race, species, gender and generation (as well as their intersection) potentially impacting the issues your project focuses on may be transformed by your activities?
 - If so, how it is done and how it could be improved?
 - If not, in which parts/tasks/focuses of your project could this be addressed and how?